

General information

In the field of scientific research, the effects of exercise programmes are regularly subjected to rigorous testing, particularly through meta-analyses, thereby establishing a solid foundation of scientific knowledge. Unfortunately, the descriptions of these programmes are often lacking in detail, which prevents clinicians from implementing them in their clinical practice. The SHADE project aims to provide clinicians with appropriate and feasible solutions, based on the latest evidence. This project has received financial support from the Swiss National Science Foundation. The initial phase of the project involved conducting a living systematic review with a network meta-analysis (LSR). This phase is still ongoing and the results have not yet been published. This LSR comprises 84 randomised controlled trials (RCTs). The main objective of this LSR is to analyse the effectiveness of different types of physical exercise in the prevention and rehabilitation of hospital-acquired disabilities (HAD) in hospitalised older adults, compared with usual care. The next phase of this project involves reaching a consensus on the two most effective exercise interventions to be implemented in an acute care hospital setting, using a Delphi study methodology.

Consequently, two Delphi studies are required, one for each of the two most effective forms of physical training. One Delphi study will focus on resistance training, whilst the other will focus on a multi-component exercise programme combining balance, resistance and walking training.

Objective of the first cycle: The objective of this first cycle is to validate the exercises and exercise protocols identified in the systematic review. It also aims to recruit a group of exercise participants and to compile a list of facilitators and barriers for clinicians and patients in a hospital setting.

Due to the wide variety of patients' needs and abilities, we will use a predetermined classification system for patients, based on the commonly used three-level dependency scale of the Barthel Index. To facilitate responses, these categories will be defined descriptively rather than by specific score thresholds on the Barthel Index:

- Totally or severely dependent: the patient is unable to perform all or part of the activities of daily living without substantial help
- Moderately dependent: the patient can perform several activities of daily living independently or with minimal help
- Slightly dependent or independent: the patient is largely independent

At the end of the first cycle, you will be asked to provide certain personal details so that we can transfer 50 CHF for each cycle you have completed. This will be done at the end of the third cycle to minimise the number of transactions. If any of your contact details change during this period, please let us know.